

**Four species of the genus *Gasteruption* LATREILLE new to Poland,
with updated checklist of Polish species (Hymenoptera,
Evanoioidea: Gasteruptionidae)**

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831884>

BOGDAN WIŚNIEWSKI

University of Rzeszów, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Land Management and Environmental Protection,
1 Ćwiklińskiej Str., 35-601 Rzeszów, Poland, e-mail: bogdan.w@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT. Four species of the genus *Gasteruption* LATREILLE (Hymenoptera: Gasteruptionidae) are recorded for the first time from Poland, namely: *G. hastator* (FABRICIUS), *G. merceti* KIEFFER, *G. nigrescens* SCHLETTERER, and *G. undulatum* (ABELLE de PERRIN). Information on distribution of the species is summarized. New localities for another two species of *Gasteruption* known so far from single records in Poland are also presented. The updated checklist of Polish Gasteruptionidae is given.

KEY WORDS: Hymenoptera, Gasteruptionidae, Poland, new records, distribution, faunistics, checklist.

INTRODUCTION

The family Gasteruptionidae is distributed worldwide, and about 500 species were described so far. The most species inhabit tropical regions; the Australian fauna is especially rich in gasteruptionid wasps (ca. 200 described species) and the most primitive forms occur there (GAULD & BOLTON 1996). The family is represented in Europe by ca. 30 species belonging to the single genus *Gasteruption* LATREILLE, 1796 (MADL 2013).

The European members of the genus are medium sized wasps with slender body (Fig. 1). Head is readily separated from pronotum by long, neck-like propleura. Antennae are 13-segmented in males, and 14 in females. Fore wings are well developed and capable of plication, with 5-6 closed cells; hind wings are smaller, with most veins reduced. Third pair of legs is elongated, with strongly clavate metatibia. Metasoma is strongly compressed, attached extremely high to propodeum, almost touching metanotum. Ovipositor conspicuous, short to exceptionally long; in some species longer than the rest of the body (Figs. 2 and 3).

Biology of most of European gasteruptionids is not known. Some of the species have been reared from nests of solitary bees and wasps placed in stems of shrubs, reed, or holes in wood. Females of *Gasteruption* can also be observed laying their eggs in the ground nests of solitary bees (O'TOOLE & RAW 1999) and in the nests situated in wooden walls (own observations). According to MANSON (1993) the larvae are predators, feeding on eggs and larvae of host species found in nests. It is stressed by the most of researchers, that gasteruptionids can only develop in the nests of solitary bees feeding either on hosts' eggs or larvae and the food stored in cells (e.g. GAULD & BOLTON 1996, MALYSHEV 1965, PAGLIANO & SCARAMOZZINO 2000, WALL 1994). According to the authors, records of sphecids and eumenid wasps as hosts are doubtful and come from mixed nests with solitary bees.

Polish fauna of Gasteruptiidae is very poorly studied. The records of members of the family can be found in the following papers: WEIGEL (1806), WIERZEJSKI (1868), BRISCHKE (1881, 1882, 1888), DITTRICH (1885), MINKIEWICZ (1935), GŁOWACKI (1953), MACKO & NOSKIEWICZ (1954), WÓJTOWSKI & SZYMAŚ (1973), GÓRNY (1979), WIŚNIEWSKI (2001, 2004, 2007, 2009, 2016), and BOGUSCH *et al.* (2018). The first checklist of Polish Gasteruptiidae was published by HUFLEJT (1997); the author listed 11 species, and 7 of them were for the first time recorded from Poland.

The present contribution brings information about four species of the genus *Gasteruption* new to the Polish fauna. There is also information about new localities for another two species known so far from single records in Poland (HUFLEJT 1997).

The aims of the paper are:

- to update the information about gasteruptiid wasps in Poland,
- to at least partly fill the gap in our knowledge of the distribution of Gasteruptiidae in the country,
- to present the updated checklist of Polish species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The records are the result of a review of specimens collected by me, the specimens housed in the collections of the Upper Silesian Museum (Bytom), and Wigry National Park (Krzywe). The collection of Jan K. Kowalczyk (Łódź) was also examined. The studied specimens are housed in the collections listed.

The species are listed in alphabetical order. The zoogeographical division of Poland follows the one accepted in the series “*Katalog Fauny Polski*” (*The Catalogue of Polish Fauna*). For each locality, the UTM code is given. Notes on biology and distribution follow mainly: OEHLKE (1984), WALL (1994), PAGLIANO & SCARAMOZZINO (2000), ZHAO *et al.* 2012, MADL (2013), ACHTERBERG & TALEBI (2014), as well as ŽIKIĆ *et al.* (2014). The images were taken with Nikon D300S camera with Micro Nikkor lens.

RESULTS

Gasteruption hastator (FABRICIUS, 1804)

Małopolska Upland: “Krzyżanowice” Nature Reserve [DA68]: 21 VI 1995 – 1 ♂, leg. R. Dobosz, 13 VII 1996 – 2 ♀♀, leg. W. Żyła; “Skowronno” Nature Reserve [DA69]: 18 VI 1995 – 1 ♂, leg. R. Dobosz.

New species in the Polish fauna.

There is information about the species published on the web site ‘insektarium.net’; two females were observed and photographed by Rafał Kaźmierczak in “Winiary Zagojskie” Nature Reserve [DA78] on 12. June, 2018 (<https://insektarium.net/hymenoptera-2/gasteruptiidae-zadziorkowate/gasteruption-hastator-zadziorek/>). All known Polish records are situated along the valley of Nida river, and the specimens were either collected or observed in xerothermophilous plant communities on gypsum hills.

The species is known from (in alphabetical order): Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Central European Russia, Corsica, Crete, Croatia, Czech

Republic, Cyclades Is., Dodecanese Is., French mainland, Germany, Greek mainland, Hungary, Iran, Near East, North Africa, Sardinia, Serbia, Sicily, Slovakia, Spanish mainland, Switzerland, Turkey, Far East of Russia (MADL 2013, ACHTERBERG & TALEBI 2014, ŽIKIĆ *et al.* 2014).

Reported from nests of wild bees of the genera *Osmia* and *Hylaeus* spp. in *Rubus* stems as well as nests of *Systropha* (ACHTERBERG & TALEBI 2014). Collected from May to August.

***Gasteruption merceti* (KIEFFER, 1904)**

Małopolska Upland: “Wzniesienia Łódzkie” Landscape Park, Plichtów [DC04]: 1 VI 2004 – 1 ♀, leg. J. K. Kowalczyk.

Sandomierska Lowland: Łętowice by Wojnicz [DA83]: 27 VI 1997 – 1 ♀, swept in the sandy area with scarce vegetation on the edge of pine forest (*Pino-Quercetum*), leg. B. Wiśniowski.

New species in the Polish fauna.

Holomediterranean species. Recorded so far from Europe (except its northern part): Albany, Austria, Bulgaria, Crete, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Montenegro, Near East, Sardinia, Serbia, Sicily, Slovakia, South European Russia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine, as well as Asia Minor, Syria and Iran (OEHLKE 1984, WALL 1994, PAGLIANO & SCARAMOZZINO 2000, MADL 2013, ACHTERBERG & TALEBI 2014, ŽIKIĆ *et al.* 2014).

The solitary bee *Ceratina cyanea* (KIRBY, 1802) (Apoidea: Anthophoridae) is listed among the possible hosts of *G. merceti* (WALL 1994, JAKUBZIK & CÖLLN 1998). The wasps are on wings from the beginning of May (JAKUBZIK & CÖLLN 1998) till August (WALL 1994). Adults visit mainly flowers of the families Apiaceae and Asteraceae.

Fig. 1. Female of *Gasteruption merceti* KIEFFER, general habitus; body length 24 mm (including ovipositor).
Ryc. 1. Samica *Gasteruption merceti* KIEFFER, widok ogólny; długość ciała 24 mm (włącznie z pokładelkiem).

Fig. 2. Female of *Gasteruption assectator* (LINNAEUS), general habitus.

Ryc. 2. Samica *Gasteruption assectator* (LINNAEUS), widok ogólny.

Gasteruption nigrescens SCHLETTERER, 1885

Mazurian Lakeland: Wigierski National Park, Cimochowizna [FE39]: 20 VII 2001 – 1 ♀, collected during netting on plants in a peat bog, leg. W. Żyła.

New species in the Polish fauna.

Not often recorded, known from the following countries and regions: Austria, Central European Russia, Croatia, Greek mainland, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Montenegro, Serbia, Slovakia, Switzerland, Turkey (MADL 2013, ACHTERBERG & TALEBI 2014, ŽIKIĆ *et al.* 2014).

Reared from nests of *Hoplitis leucomelana* (KIRBY, 1802) and *Heriades rubicola* PÉREZ, 1890 (BOGUSCH *et al.* 2018).

Gasteruption opacum (TOURNIER, 1877)

Mazurian Lakeland: Rubcowo [FE56]: 3 VIII 1977 – 2 ♀♀, leg. J.K. Kowalczyk.

Kraków-Wieluń Upland: “Załęczański” Landscape Park, “Węże” Nature Reserve [CB46]: 3 VII 1998 – 1 ♀, leg. J.K. Kowalczyk.

Fig. 3. Female of *Gasteruption jaculator* (LINNAEUS), general habitus.

Ryc. 3. Samica *Gasteruption jaculator* (LINNAEUS), widok ogólny.

Małopolska Upland: Pasturka near Pińczów [DA69]: 13 VII 1996 – 1 ♂, leg. W. Żyła.

Known so far from Gutkowo near Olsztyn (HUFLEJT 1997), Bytom and Ojców National Park (WIŚNIEWSKI 2004).

The species is known from: Austria, Belgium, Corsica, Crete, Croatia, Czech Republic, Dodecanese Is., French mainland, Germany, Greek mainland, Hungary, Italian mainland, Iran, Montenegro, Norwegian mainland, Poland, Sardinia, Serbia, Sicily, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spanish mainland, Switzerland, Turkey (MADL 2013, ACHTERBERG & TALEBI 2014, ŽIKIĆ *et al.* 2014).

Biology unknown.

Gasteruption subtile (THOMSON, 1883)

Western Beskid Mts: Babia Góra [CV99]: 12 VII 1990 – 1 ♀, leg. R. Dobosz.

Nowotarska Basin: Vicinity of Jurgów [DV36]: 29 VII 1997 – 2 ♀♀ leg. W. Żyła; Jurgów [DV36]: 2 VIII 2000 – 1 ♀, leg. W. Żyła.

Known so far only from 1 female collected in 1949 in Zawoja-Barańcowa (HUFLEJT 1997), which is situated in the foot of the Babia Góra mountain in Western Beskid. All known records of the species in Poland are in Carpathians (S Poland).

Rarely reported, known so far from: Austria, Central European Russia, Croatia, Finland, French mainland, Germany, Hungary, Italian mainland, Sweden, Switzerland (MADL 2013, ŽIKIĆ *et al.* 2014).

Biology unknown.

Gasteruption undulatum (ABEILLE de PERRIN, 1879)

Pomeranian Lakeland: Słowiński National Park, Rowy [XA35]: 31 VII 2004 – 1 ♀, swept on sand dune, leg. W. Żyła.

Upper Silesia: Bytom, Dąbrowa Miejska [CA48]: 26 VII 2003 – 1 ♂, on flowers of Apiaceae, leg. W. Żyła.

New species in the Polish fauna.

The species is reported from Poland on ‘Fauna Europaea’ website (MADL 2013) but only as the listing of countries, without any detailed information. I have not found any published record of the species from Poland, and thus I regard it as new to the Polish fauna. Reported from the following countries and regions: Austria, Balearic Is., Belgium, Bulgaria, Corsica, Croatia, Czech Republic, Cyclades Is., Dodecanese Is., Finland, French mainland, Germany, Greek mainland, Italian mainland, Portuguese mainland, Sardinia, Serbia, Slovakia, Spanish mainland, Switzerland, Turkey (MADL 2013, ACHTERBERG & TALEBI 2014, ŽIKIĆ *et al.* 2014).

Biology unknown.

Checklist of Polish species of the genus *Gasteruption* LATREILLE, 1796:

1. *Gasteruption assectator* (LINNAEUS, 1758)
2. *Gasteruption caucasicum* (GUÉRIN-MÉNEVILLE, 1844)
= *Gasteruption pedemontanum* (TOURNIER, 1877) (synonymised by ACHTERBERG, 2013)
3. *Gasteruption diversipes* (ABEILLE de PERRIN, 1879)
4. *Gasteruption erythrostomum* (DAHLBOM, 1831)
5. *Gasteruption freyi* (TOURNIER, 1877)
6. *Gasteruption hastator* (FABRICIUS, 1804)
7. *Gasteruption jaculator* (LINNAEUS, 1758)
8. *Gasteruption laticeps* (TOURNIER, 1877)
9. *Gasteruption merceti* KIEFFER, 1904
10. *Gasteruption minutum* (TOURNIER, 1877)
11. *Gasteruption nigrescens* SCHLETTERER, 1885
12. *Gasteruption opacum* (TOURNIER, 1877)
13. *Gasteruption subtile* (THOMSON, 1883)
14. *Gasteruption tournieri* SCHLETTERER, 1885
15. *Gasteruption undulatum* (ABEILLE de PERRIN, 1879)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The following persons contributed in many ways: Mr Jan Krzysztof Kowalczyk, Dr Roland Dobosz, and Waldemar Żyła have made their collections available for my studies; Mr Tomasz Huflejt (Museum and Institute of Zoology PAS, Warsaw) has either verified or determined the specimens of *Gasteruption* and made many valuable comments to the manuscript; Mr Guido Pagliano (Italy) has kindly donated some specimens of Gasteruptiidae for my comparative collection. I would like to thank all of them for their support, as well as the curators from the institutions mentioned above.

REFERENCES

- ACHTERBERG C. van 2013. De nederlandse hongerwespen (Hymenoptera: Evanioidea: Gasteruptiidae). *Nederlandse Faunistische Mededelingen* 39: 55–87.
- ACHTERBERG C. van, TALEBI A.A. 2014. Review of *Gasteruption* LATREILLE (Hymenoptera, Gasteruptiidae) from Iran and Turkey, with the description of 15 new species. *Zookeys* 458: 1–187.
- BOGUSCH P., ACHTERBERG C. van, ŠILHÁN K., ASTAPENKOVÁ A., HENEGER P. 2018. Description of mature larvae and ecological notes on *Gasteruption* LATREILLE (Hymenoptera, Evanioidea, Gasteruptiidae) parasitizing hymenopterans nesting in reed galls. *Journal of Hymenoptera Research* 65: 1–21.
- BRISCHKE C.G.A. 1881. Die Ichneumoniden der Provinzen West- und Ostpreussen. *Bericht des Westpreussischen Botanisch-Zoologischen Vereins* 4: 104–167.
- BRISCHKE C.G.A. 1882. Die Ichneumoniden der Provinzen West- und Ostpreussen. *Schriften der Naturforschenden Gesellschaft in Danzig, Neue Folge* 5(3): 121–183.
- BRISCHKE C.G.A. 1888. Bericht über eine Excursion nach Hela während des Juli 1887. *Schriften der Naturforschenden Gesellschaft in Danzig, Neue Folge* 7(1): 42–64.
- DITTRICH [R.]. 1885. [Über die Schlupfwespengattung *Foenus* (Evaniidae)]. *Zeitschrift für Entomologie, Neue Folge* 10: XVII–XVIII.
- GAULD I., BOLTON B. 1996. The Hymenoptera. Oxford University Press, New York: 1–332.
- GŁOWACKI J. 1953. Przyczynek do znajomości błonkówek (Hymenoptera) okolic Warszawy. *Fragmenta Faunistica Musei Zoologici Polonici* 6: 501–523.
- GÓRNY S. 1979. Pasożytnicze błonkówki na olszy czarnej — *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) GAERTN. w okolicach Ostródy. *Polskie Pismo Entomologiczne* 49: 305–369.
- HUFLEJT T. 1997. Gasteruptiidae, pp. 116–117, In: RAZOWSKI J. (Ed.), Checklist of animals of Poland 5.
- JAKUBZIK A., CÖLLN K. 1998. *Gasteruption merceti* KIEFFER, 1904 (Hymenoptera: Gasteruptiidae) Erstnachweis für den Nordwesten von Rheinland-Pfalz. *Dendrocopos* 25: 211–213.
- MACKO S., NOSKIEWICZ J. 1954. Stanowisko rozchodnika białego (*Sedum album* L.) na Górze Wapiennej koło Stolca pod Żąbkowicami. *Ochrona Przyrody* 22: 167–194.
- MADL M. (2013) Fauna Europaea: Gasteruptiidae, In: MITROIU M.-D. (2013), Fauna Europaea: Hymenoptera, Ants, Bees and Wasps. Fauna Europaea version 2017.06. <https://fauna-eu.org>.
- MALYSHEV S.I. 1965. Lebensweise und Instinkte der primitiven Schlupfwespen Gasteruptiidae (Hymenoptera). *Zoologische Jahrbücher. Abteilung für Systematik, Ökologie und Geographie der Tiere* 92: 239–288.
- MANSON W.R.M. 1993. Superfamilies Evanioidea, Stephanoidea, Megalyroidea, and Trigonalynoidea, pp. 510–520, In: GOULET H., HUBER J.T. (Eds.) Hymenoptera of the world: an identification guide to families. Agriculture Canada.
- MINKIEWICZ R. 1935. *Myrmosa brunripes* LEPEL. et autres Hyménoptères Aculéates méridionaux ou rares, trouvés en Pologne centrale (en relation avec les aggregations de nidification respectives). *Fragmenta Faunistica Musei Zoologici Polonici* 2: 189–227, Pl. IX.
- OEHLEKE J. 1984. Beiträge zur Insektenfauna der DDR: Hymenoptera — Evanioidea, Stephanoidea, Trigonalynoidea (Insecta). Faunistische Abhandlungen. *Staatliches Museum für Tierkunde in Dresden* 11(13): 161–190.
- O'TOOLE C., RAW A. 1999. Bees of the world. Blandford: 192 pp.
- PAGLIANO G., SCARAMOZZINO P.L. 2000. Gasteruptiidae italiani (Hymenoptera: Evanioidea). *Bolletino del Museo Regionale di Scienze Naturali, Torino* 17: 5–38.
- WALL I. 1994. Seltene Hymenopteren aus Mittel-, West- und Südeuropa (Hymenoptera Apocrita: Stephanoidea, Evanioidea, Trigonalynoidea). Entomofauna. *Zeitschrift für Entomologie* 15(14): 137–184.

- WEIGEL J.A.V. 1806. Geographische, naturhistorische und technologische Beschreibung des souverainen Herzogthums Schlesien. Zehnter Theil. Verzeichniß der bisher entdeckten, in Schlesien lebenden Thiere. Himbürg Buchhandlung, Berlin, VIII + 358 pp.
- WIERZEJSKI A. 1868. Przyczynek do fauny owadów błonkoskrzydłych (Hymenoptera). *Sprawozdanie Komisji Fizyograficznej c.k. Towarzystwa Naukowego Krakowskiego* 2: 108–120.
- WIŚNIEWSKI B. 2001. Błonkówki (Hymenoptera) polskich Bieszczadów ze szczególnym uwzględnieniem Bieszczadzkiego Parku Narodowego. *Monografie bieszczadzkie* 8: 145–187.
- WIŚNIEWSKI B. 2004. Nowe stanowiska gatunków z rodzaju *Gasteruption* LATREILLE, 1796 (Hymenoptera: Gasteruptionidae) w Polsce. *Wiadomości entomologiczne* 23(2): 117–118.
- WIŚNIEWSKI B. 2007. Dodatki do fauny błonkówek (Insecta, Hymenoptera) Ojcowskiego Parku Narodowego. *Prądnik. Prace i materiały Muzeum im. prof. Władysława Szafera* 17: 131–148.
- WIŚNIEWSKI B. 2009. Błonkówki Ojcowskiego Parku Narodowego, pp. 617–642, In: KLASA A., PARTYKA J. (Eds.), *Monografia Ojcowskiego Parku Narodowego. Przyroda*.
- WIŚNIEWSKI B. 2016. Katalog błonkówek (Arthropoda: Insecta: Hymenoptera) Ojcowskiego Parku Narodowego. *Prądnik. Prace i materiały Muzeum im. prof. Władysława Szafera* 26: 95–146.
- WÓJTOWSKI F., SZYMAŚ B. 1974. Entomofauna pasożytnicza i towarzysząca pszczołom samotniczym (Apidae solitariae) w pułapkach gniazdowych. *Roczniki Akademii Rolniczej w Poznaniu* 66[1973]: 171–179.
- ZHAO K.-X., ACHTERBERG C. van, XU Z.-F. 2012. A revision of Chinese Gasteruptionidae (Hymenoptera, Evanioidea). *Zookeys* 237: 1–123.
- ŽIKIĆ V., ACHTERBERG C. van, STANKOVIĆ S.S., DUBAIĆ J.B., ČETKOVIĆ A. 2014. Review of the Gasteruptionidae (Hymenoptera: Evanioidea) from the territory of the former Yugoslavia, with three newly reported species. *Zootaxa* 3793(5): 573–586.

Accepted: 13 May 2020; published: 18 May 2020

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution License <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>